

First culture of *Dinophysis acuminata* from southern Chile: Ecophysiology, toxin production and phylogeny

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Abstract

In Chile *Dinophysis acuminata* is a conspicuous mixotrophic dinoflagellate inhabit on Ocean Pacific Coast (OPC) and Patagonian fjords (PF). In this study, for the first time, we evaluated the effects of light and temperature on the growth and the toxin production of the culture strains of *D. acuminata* isolated from southern Chile. The phylogenetic analysis also was carried out using the COI marker. Strains were isolated in 2019-2020 from the OPC and PF and were maintained in culture feeding with *M. rubrum* as prey. Higher growth rates and cell abundances were observed at 45 compared to 90 and 125 $\mu\text{mol photon m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. However, growth rates were equivalent at both 12°C and 15 °C. Toxins screening revealed the presence of pecteno-toxins 2 (PTX2) in six strains isolated from OPC and PF, but okadaic acid and dynophysistoxin were not detected. PTX2 concentration was not affected by temperature and light, showing values ranging from 3.920 to 14.077 pg cell⁻¹. The Chilean *D. acuminata* sequences clustered in the “*Dinophysis acuminata* complex” clade showing among sequences genetic distances ranging from 0.000 and 0.001. Further work is needed to know with major precision the environmental effects on growth and toxin biogeography

Keywords: *Dinophysis acuminata*, ecophysiology, toxins production, culture, Chile, phylogeny

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Introduction

Dinophysis acuminata is a cosmopolitan species that has been recorded along different coastal zones around the world (Ha Park *et al.*, 2019). This species is responsible for diarrhetic shellfish poisoning (DSP) due to the production of the okadaic acid (OA) and dinophysistoxins (DTXs). Also, some populations can produce pecteno-toxins (PTXs), but there is no evidence that PTXs are toxic to humans. However, due to their toxicity by intraperitoneal injection in mouse bioassays, these toxins are regulated in the European community, Canada and New Zealand.

In Chile, *D. acuminata* is distributed along the Ocean Pacific coast and within the Patagonian fjords where have formed blooms that represent a threat to public health, artisanal fisheries and the aquaculture industry. Despite the years of studying this species and the relevant information obtained, for example from oceanographic studies, cultures of *D. acuminata* not yet been performed.

In this work, for the first time, we established single cell cultures of *D. acuminata* and investigated their taxonomy as well as how environmental conditions effect growth rates and toxin production.

Material and Methods

Strain isolation

Between 2019 and 2020 *Dinophysis acuminata* strains were isolated from plankton samples taken from Patagonian Fjords (FDAM1, FDAM2 and FDAM3) and from Ocean Pacific (PDAM1, PDAM2, and PDAM3) ecosystems (Figure 1). Cells were

deposited in multiple well plate (48 wells), were fed with *Mesodinium rubrum* and this was fed with *Teleaulax amphioxi*. Cells were maintained at 45 $\mu\text{mol photon m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ light intensity, 12 °C, 16:8 L:D photoperiod, 33 \pm 1 salinity, and (f/2) 1/3 culture medium.

DNA extraction, amplification, sequencing and phylogeny

Dinophysis acuminata culture free-prey were harvested and concentrated by centrifugation at 1500g for 10 min at 4 °C, the supernatant discarded and the cell pellets incubated at 65 °C for one h in 10 μL Proteinase K (10 mg mL^{-1}) and 1 mL cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB). The Dinocox1F and Dinocox1R primers (in: Ha Park *et al.*, 2019) were used to amplify a segment of the *cox1* gene. Phylogenetic analyses were performed using alignments of 673 bp along with sequences available in GenBank using ClustalW/Geneious Prime 2019.0.3 (Larkin *et al.*, 2007). Then Bayesian analysis was conducted using MrBayes V3.1.2 under the appropriate model (GTR + I) (Ronquist and Huelsenbeck, 2003).

Light microscopy

Two sets of *D. acuminata* cells photography were taken: (1) in the exponential phase of growth and (2) in cultures c.a. three months after prey species was added. Images were taken with a camera implemented in a Zeiss AXIO VERT A1 inverted microscope.

Growth under different light intensity and temperature

Strain PDAM1 was used to evaluate growth under different levels of light intensity and

temperature. The first experiment measured growth rates of *D. acuminata* at 45, 95 and 125 $\mu\text{mol photon m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. The second experiment evaluated the strain growth at 90 and 45 $\mu\text{mol photon m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$, and temperatures of 12 and 15 °C. In the experiments, strains were maintained using 16:8 L:D photoperiod, 33 ± 1 salinity and (f/2) 1/3 culture medium. The first experiment began with *D. acuminata* abundance of 30 cells mL^{-1} and 5,000 cell mL^{-1} of *M. rubrum*. The second experiment, beginning with 100 cells mL^{-1} of *D. acuminata* 2,000 cell mL^{-1} of *M. rubrum*. Periodically samples were taken (three replicate), fixed with Lugol and counted under inverted microscopy. At the same time, PDAM2, PDAM3, FDAM2 and FDAM3 strains were maintained at 45 $\mu\text{mol photon m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ light intensity and 15 °C temperature and were fed with 2,000 cells mL^{-1} of *M. rubrum*. After ca. 48 days, strains were filtered for toxin analysis.

Growth rate and maximum cell abundance

The growth rate of *D. acuminata* was determined through a linear regression model $\gamma_i = \alpha + \beta\chi_i$ (Guillard and Hargraves, 1993), where $\gamma_i = \ln$ -transformed cell density (cells mL^{-1}); $\chi_i = \text{time}$ (days); $\alpha = \text{intercept}$; and $\beta = \text{growth rate}$ (cells div day^{-1}). The maximum cell density at the end of the exponential phase was used as the maximum cell density response (cells mL^{-1}).

Cell toxin production

Cells were filtered through 47 mm diameter glass fiber filters (GF/F Whatman) and the filter was transferred to a 2 mL Eppendorf tube with 1 mL of Methanol 100%. The tubes were placed in a container with ice, sonicated five times for 5 s. After 10 min the solution was filtered using PVDF syringe, filters of 0.22 μm

pore size and 3 mm diameter, and the solution pass-through was deposited in HPLC vials of 1.8 mL. To estimate toxins concentration, selected reaction monitoring (SRM) measurements were performed on a triple quadrupole mass spectrometer (Agilent 6420) equipped with an Electrospray ionization (ESI) source, coupled to 1290 UHPLC system (Agilent, Palo Alto, CA, U.S.A.). The chromatographic separation of Lipophilic Toxins (LTs) and Domoic acid (DA) after injection of 2.5 μl of a sample, was performed by reverse-phase chromatography using a SunShell C18 column (100 x 2.1 mm id, 2.6 μm particle size) at 40°C according to Braña-Magdalena *et al.* (2014). Certified reference standards, of okadaic acid, pectenotoxin-2, dynophysistoxin-1, dynophysistoxin-2, were used, and obtained from the National Research Council of Canada (Halifax, Canada).

Results and Discussion

The phylogenetic analysis of the Chilean COI sequences showed they all fell within the “*Dinophysis acuminata* species complex” clade. This clade was supported by a posterior Bayesian probability of 1.0. The genetic distance among Chilean COI sequences ranged from 0.000 to 0.001. Other species whose COI sequences fell in the same clade as those from the Chilean isolates included *D. sacculus* Stein 1883, and *D. ovum* Schütt, 1895. Previous work indicated COI genes were sufficient to delineate *D. acuminata* complex species. Our results, in contrast, indicated COI gene lacked the ability to distinguish these species.

Both strains showed similar morphological variation along their growth phase. In the exponential phase, length and depth

measurements both strains had greater than after three months of culture without addition of prey cells. In exponential phase, the contour of the largest hypothetical plate was in the major part symmetrical in relation to the longitudinal axis. A small number of asymmetrical forms were also observed. After three months of culture similar forms were observed but asymmetrical form was more evident (Figs. 2, 3). Comparable cells forms have been observed in the strains cultured in the northern hemisphere (Ha Park *et al.*, 2019).

The first experiment revealed low growth at highest light intensity of $125 \mu\text{mol photon m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ (Fig. 4). In turn, in the second experiment different light levels did effect growth rates, but not temperature over the range investigated (Tables 1 and 2). In the field has been observed the stratification of this species, founding high abundance around the pycnocline (Diaz *et al.*, 2011). Perhaps in the surface, where high light intensity occurs, *D. acuminata* suffer growth inhibition.

Fig. 1. Zones where strains were isolated, in Los Lagos (red point) and Aysén (Yellow point) regions of Chile.

Toxin production was not affected by either light intensity or temperature (Table 3). PTX2 was the only toxin found in the six strains assessed that were isolated from both Patagonian fjords and Pacific Ocean coast. No OA or DTXs were detected. A similar toxin pattern was reported by Fux *et al.*, (2011) using a strain isolated from the Reloncavi Sound. However, in the extreme south of Chile the presence of the dinophysistoxins was found in shellfish, and the only species recorded at this time in the water column was *D. acuminata*, which was the presumable species implicated in the DSP event (Uribe *et al.*, 2001).

This work presents for the first time the ecophysiology, genetic identification and toxin production of *D. acuminata* strains isolated from contrasting environments in

southern Chile. However, further work using more environmental drivers and levels, and strains isolated along coastal Chile, are needed to know with major precision the environmental effects on growth and toxin biogeography.

Fig. 2. PDAM1 strain isolated from Ocean Pacific coast. A - F cells in the exponential growth. G - R cells after three months of culture.

Fig. 3. FDAM1 strain isolated from Patagonian Fjords. A - G cells in the exponential growth. H - M, cells after three months of culture.

Table 1. Growth of PDAM1 strain. GR: growth rate. SE: standard error. Tuk: Tukey HSD posteriority test. MCA: maximum cell density (Cells mL⁻¹).

Light	GR	SE	Tuk.	MCA	SE	Tuk.
45	0.138	0.008	a	829	138	b
95	0.094	0.004	b	453	94	ab
125	0.054	0.005	c	153	11	a

Fig. 4. Growth of PDAM1 strain under different light intensities.

Table 2. Growth of PDAM1. Tem: Temperature. GR: growth rate. SE: standard error. MCA: maximum cell density (Cells mL⁻¹).

Tem.	Light	GR	SE	MCA	SE
12	45	0.052	0.008	700	175
12	95	0.047	0.012	607	115
15	45	0.064	0.007	907	142
15	95	0.027	0.011	407	86

Table 3. Toxin production (pg cell⁻¹) of the strain PDAM1. SE: standard error.

Tem	Light	PTX2	SE
12	45	3.920	0.776
12	95	7.591	3.736
15	45	4.497	1.575
15	95	14.077	8.190

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